

THE WAY OF EXPRESSING CONFLICTS IN MARK TWAIN'S WRITING

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ABSTRACT

The article tried to show the analysis of expressing the conflicts in Mark Twain's writing and all represent different people, groups, or concepts that had an active part during the period. The goal of this article is to motivate language learners to know theme what was conflict between children and adults realistic novels to highlight ploys of manipulation.

Key words: Huckleberry Finn, conflict, external, characters, expressing conflicts, novel, research

INTRODUCTION

Conflict is one of the elements that are essential in the development of element of literature. Even a literary work particularly novel if there is not a conflict, so the novel would be less attractive because of the story in the novel feels flat.

Conflict is motivated by differences in the characteristics that brought the individual in an interaction. The differences among them are related to the physical characteristics, intelligence, knowledge, customs, beliefs, and so forth. With it accompanies individual characteristics in social interaction, conflict is a normal situation in any society and any society is not one who has never experienced a conflict

between its members or with other community groups, the conflict will only disappear with the loss of society itself.

First, forms of inner conflict experienced by the main character covers a conflict between choices that are not in accordance with the desire, hesitancy in dealing with problems, and expectations which does not match with his reality. From the research, show that over all problems faced by the main character is dominated by id rather than ego. Domination of id than ego that causes the main character has inner conflict, while the form of inner conflict of the most dominant on the main characters itself are at variance indecision in dealing with problems.

Second, the emergence factors of inner conflict of the main character in the novel *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn* by Mark Twain are divides into two categories, namely internal factors and external factors. Internal factors, the emergence of internal conflict in this novel comes from inside the main character, the desire to be free man, because the pressure of the rules given by the Widow Douglas and Miss Watson, and anxious on a choice. External factors experienced by the main character comes from the society around the Mississippi river, lies that have been done when protect Jim, and lies when he wants to steal the possessions of Mary Jane. Based on the research above the factors behind the inner conflict of the main character in the novel *The Adventures of Huckleberry finn* can be conclude that the inner conflict on the main character is an external factors, especially in relation between the main character and the society around him.

The third, inner conflict in the novel *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn* can be solved by the main character. The solving of inner conflict on the main characters includes, sublimation embodied in close his self by not communicating to others, repression or suppression manifested in variants attempted suicide, projections embodied in variant severed ties with home and repeatedly ran away from home, and rationalization variants manifest in the decision to live independently with life as he wants.

Based on research on the inner conflict of the solving of the problems in the main character in the novel *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn* can be concludes that in solving of the problem the main character often use the projections, the most widely realized by the main character when he fled from the house.

CONCLUSION

This article looked at expressing conflicts in *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn* which written by Mark Twain. We can study the some special features of conflicts in this work. *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn* will undoubtedly have a bright pay to investigate this kind of expressing of conflicts.

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